

Design and Modeling of a 2-DOF Decoupled Rotation Platform for Micro-manipulation

Cunman Liang, Fujun Wang*, Yanling Tian, Dawei Zhang

Key Laboratory of Mechanism Theory and Equipment Design of Ministry of Education

Tianjin University

Tianjin 300072, China

lcm@tju.edu.cn, wangfujun@tju.edu.cn, meytian@tju.edu.cn, medzhang@tju.edu.cn

Abstract—In high precision micro-manipulation task, precision angle adjustment is very important, which directly affects the quality of micro-manipulation. In this paper a novel 2-DOF (degree of freedom) rotation platform driven by two piezoelectric (PZT) actuators is designed to realize precision angle adjustment. The rotation platform has compact flexure-based mechanical structure and light weight. The rotation decoupling in X- and Y-axes are realized through the Hook joint. In order to obtain large range rotational angle, bridge-type mechanism is utilized in the 2-DOF rotation platform. An analytical model for rotational angle and input stiffness calculation is established. The influences of key parameters on the rotational angle as well as input stiffness of the rotation platform are analyzed. Finite element analysis (FEA) is conducted to evaluate the analytical model. The results of FEA fit the analytical model well and show the rotation platform exhibits good performance.

Keywords—rotation platform, rotation decoupling, structure design, flexure hinge

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently the biological engineering, material science, microelectronics industry are developing rapidly. The precision micro-manipulation in related industries is developing toward ultra-micronization as the operated objects in micro-manipulation become smaller and smaller [1-3]. In order to guarantee the quality of precision operation, the angle adjustment in nano/micro scale is very essential [4, 5]. As a key component of precision micro-manipulation system, 2-DOF (degree of freedom) rotation platform, which is employed to execute rotational operations in X- and Y- axes, plays an important role during the operation process. The 2-DOF rotation platform will affect the quality and accuracy of micro-manipulation directly.

Now the 2-DOF rotation in X- and Y- axes is usually realized by multiple DOF platforms. There have been many studies on the multiple DOF positioning platforms. According to the different actuations, such as voice coil motor [6], linear motor [7] and piezoelectric (PZT) actuator [8] etc., many different multiple DOF precision platforms are designed. Compared with other actuators the PZT actuator has the advantages of small volume, large output force, fast response and zero backlash [9-11], so it has been widely used in precision positioning platforms. Zhang et.al [12] designed a

novel 3-DOF micro-positioning platform, which is optimized for applications such as improving the machining precision of precision grinders. Palpacelli et.al [13] designed a redundantly actuated 2-DOF platform which is driven by three linear actuators. Kim et.al [14] designed an ultra-precision 3-DOF (z , θ_x , θ_y) vertical positioning system with nanometer precision. The stroke of the translational movement is 190 mm and the stroke of the rotational movement is 0.5 mrad. However, most researchers paid attentions on the translation and rotation mixing platform which will use more actuators than the pure 2-DOF rotation platform. Moreover the rotations in X- and Y-axes of most current rotation platform are coupled, which will lead that the control of this kind platform is difficult than the 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform.

In this paper a novel 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform is designed which is driven by two PZT actuators. Based on the Hook joint the rotation decoupling in X- and Y- axes are realized. In order to obtain large range rotational angle the bridge-type mechanism is utilized in the designed platform. An analytical model is established to analysis the characteristics of the 2-DOF rotation platform. Based on the analytical model the rotational angle and input stiffness can be calculated and the influences of key parameters on the performance of the rotation platform are obtained. Finally, finite element analysis (FEA) is used to evaluate the analytical model.

II. STRUCTURE DESIGN OF 2-DOF ROTATION PLATFORM

In order to obtain precision angle adjustment in X- and Y-axes, a novel 2-DOF rotation platform is designed, which is driven by two PZT actuators. Since the displacement generated by PZT actuator is very small, an amplification mechanism is essential to obtain large range rotation angle. The bridge-type mechanism has a compact structure, a large displacement amplification ratio, and a high-frequency mode, so we use the bridge-type mechanism as the amplification mechanism in the 2-DOF rotation platform. The Hook joint has two vertical rotational axes and the rotation axes intersect at the center of the Hook joint allowing an ideal kinematic behavior of pure rotation. Therefore the Hook joint can be utilized in the 2-DOF rotation platform to realize the rotation decoupling in X- and Y- axes are realized.

Fig. 1 Mechanism of the 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform.

Figure 1 shows the mechanism of the designed 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform which is driven by two PZT actuators. The structure of 2-DOF rotation platform consists of base, bridge-type mechanism, Hook joint, pillar and upper platform. As shown in Fig. 1, two PZT actuators are installed in bridge-type mechanism. The two bridge-type mechanisms and the pillar are both fixed on the base, and through three Hook joints the upper platform connects with the bridge-type mechanisms and the pillar. The two bridge-type mechanisms are vertically arranged, and the pillar locates at the intersection point of the longitudinal axes of the bridge-type mechanisms.

When a voltage is applied on the X-axis PZT actuator, the actuator will expand and push the bridge-type mechanism. Then the bridge-type mechanism will pull the upper platform through Hook joint on the bridge-type mechanism in X-axis. The Hook joint fixed on the pillar as well as the Hook joint on the bridge-type mechanism in Y-axis will bend in Y-axis, which will lead the upper platform rotated in the Y-axis. After power is switched off, the PZT actuator will shorten to its initial length, and this causes the upper platform retract to its initial position under the elastic force of flexible hinge. When a voltage is applied on the Y-axis PZT actuator, the upper platform will be rotated in the X-axis, which is the same with the rotation in Y-axis. During the working process the PZT actuator and bridge-type mechanism in X-axis (or Y-axis) will not be affected by the rotation in Y-axis (or X-axis). Therefore the rotation decoupling in X- and Y- axes has been realized, which means that the decoupling control is not needed, so the controllability of 2-DOF rotation platform will be greatly improved.

III. MODELING OF 2-DOF ROTATION PLATFORM

As the key component of the 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform, the Hook joint directly affects the performance of the rotation platform. Figure 2 show the structure of the Hook joint, which has two rotational axes. In each rotational axis the Hook joint can be divided into three type flexure hinges, A-type, B-type and C-type flexure hinges, which are shown in Fig. 3. The definitions of the geometric parameters are also given in Figs. 2 and 3, i.e., the minimal thickness of the Hook joint t_h ; the hinge thickness h , and the radius of the hinge r_h . A Cartesian

coordinate is located at the central point of each type flexure hinge. The shape function for of the Hook hinge is

$$\begin{cases} s(x) = t_h + 2r_h - 2\sqrt{r_h^2 - x^2} \\ w(x) = h - t_h - 2r_h - 2\sqrt{r_h^2 - x^2} \end{cases} \quad -r_h < x < r_h \quad (1)$$

Based on the integration of beam theory, the angular deflection about z-axis at position x within the hinge is determined by

$$\alpha_z = \int_{-r_h}^x \frac{M(x)}{EI_z(x)} dx \quad -r_h < x < r_h \quad (2)$$

where E is the Young's Modulus of the material, $M(x)$ and $I_z(x)$ are the inner moment and the area moment of inertia at position x within the hinge, respectively.

In order to simplify the integration, an intermediate variable θ is introduced such that:

Fig. 2 The structure of the Hook hinge: (a) overall structure and (b) section view.

Fig. 3 Different type flexure hinges of Hook joint: (a) A-type flexure hinge (b) B-type flexure hinge and (c) C-type flexure hinge.

$$x = r_h \sin \theta \quad -\frac{\pi}{2} < \theta < \frac{\pi}{2} \quad (3)$$

Substituting Eq. (3) into Eq. (2), the integration between $[-r_h, r_h]$ in x can be transferred to the interval of $[-\pi/2, \pi/2]$ in θ . If only M_z is applied, the angular deflection of each type flexure hinge is obtained:

$$\alpha_{zA} = \frac{24r_h M_z}{E} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos \theta}{(t_h + 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)^3 (h - t_h - 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)} d\theta \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{24r_h M_z}{E} P_1$$

$$\alpha_{zB} = \frac{12r_h M_z}{E} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos \theta}{(t_h + 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)^4} d\theta = \frac{12r_h M_z}{E} P_2 \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha_{zC} = \alpha_{zA} = \frac{24r_h M_z}{E} P_1 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } P_1 = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos \theta}{(t_h + 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)^3 (h - t_h - 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)} d\theta,$$

$$P_2 = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \frac{\cos \theta}{(t_h + 2r_h - 2r_h \cos \theta)^4} d\theta.$$

A-type, B-type and C-type flexure hinges are connected in parallel to form the Hook joint. Therefore the rotational stiffness of the Hook joint in one can be calculated as

$$k_{rh} = \frac{E(P_1 + P_2)}{12r_h P_1 P_2} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 4 Structure of bridge-type mechanism.

Figure 4 shows the structure of bridge-type mechanism. Assume that each flexure hinge has a 2-DOF compliance coming from the rotational and translational deformations, and other elements are rigid bodies. The amplification ratio of the bridge-type mechanism under no-load condition can be calculated as

$$\lambda = \frac{k_{ib} l_a^2 \cos^3 \alpha \sin \alpha}{2k_{rb} + k_{ib} l_a^2 \cos^2 \alpha \sin^2 \alpha} \quad (8)$$

where $l_a = \sqrt{(l_1 + 2r_b)^2 + l_2^2}$, $\alpha = \arctan\left(\frac{l_1 + 2r_b}{l_2}\right)$, k_{ib} and k_{rb} are the translational stiffness and rotational stiffness, respectively.

However, the bridge-type mechanism in the designed 2-DOF rotation platform is not under no-load condition any more. The other parts of the rotation platform affect the performance of the bridge-type mechanism, inevitably.

The compliance equation of the flexure hinge can be written as follows

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} c_{11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ 0 & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{F} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the load vector $\mathbf{F} = [F_x, F_y, M_z]^T$, \mathbf{D} is the displacement vector $\mathbf{D} = [d_x, d_y, \theta_z]^T$ and \mathbf{C} is the compliance matrix.

Based on the geometric relationship the following relationships can be obtained [15]

$$\Delta x = \left(c_{11} + \frac{l_2^2 c_{33}}{4} \right) F_{in} + \left(\frac{l_2 c_{32}}{2} - \frac{l_1 l_2 c_{33}}{4} \right) F_{out} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta y = \left(\frac{c_{23}}{2} + \frac{l_1 c_{33}}{4} \right) l_2 F_{in} + \left(c_{22} + \frac{l_1 c_{32}}{2} - \frac{l_1 c_{23}}{2} - \frac{l_1^2 c_{33}}{4} \right) F_{out} \quad (10)$$

where Δx and Δy represent the input and output displacements of the bridge arm, respectively.

For the circular hinge in the bridge-type mechanism, the parameter in compliance matrix can be calculated as:

$$c_{11} = \frac{1}{Eh_b} \left[\pi \left(\frac{r_b}{t_b} \right)^{1/2} - \frac{\pi}{2} \right] \quad (11)$$

$$c_{22} = \frac{9\pi r_b^{5/2}}{2Eh_b t_b^{5/2}} + \frac{3\pi r_b^{3/2}}{2Eh_b t_b^{3/2}} \quad (12)$$

$$c_{33} = \frac{9\pi r_b^{1/2}}{2Eh_b t_b^{5/2}} \quad (13)$$

$$c_{23} = c_{32} = \frac{9\pi r_b^{3/2}}{2Eh_b t_b^{5/2}} \quad (14)$$

where h_b is the thickness of flexure hinge, t_b is the minimal thickness of flexure hinge, r_b is the radius of flexure hinge.

The rotational angle in each axis of the 2-DOF rotation platform can be obtained

$$\theta_r = \frac{2\Delta y}{L} = \frac{F_{out} L}{2k_{rh}} \quad (15)$$

where L is the horizontal distance from center the bridge-type mechanism to the center of the pillar.

When a small displacement d_{in} from the PZT actuator is applied to the input terminal of the rotation platform, the upper platform will rotate a certain angle. Substituting Eqs. (9) and (10) into Eq. (15), the following equation can be got

$$\theta_r = \frac{2\Delta y}{L} = \frac{a_3 L d_{in}}{a_1 (L^2 - 4a_4 k_{rh}) + 4a_2 a_3 k_{rh}} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{where } a_1 = c_{11} + \frac{l_2^2 c_{33}}{4}, \quad a_2 = \frac{l_2 c_{32}}{2} - \frac{l_1 l_2 c_{33}}{4}, \quad a_3 = \frac{l_2 c_{23}}{2} + \frac{l_1 l_2 c_{33}}{4},$$

$$a_4 = c_{22} + \frac{l_1 c_{32}}{2} - \frac{l_1 c_{23}}{2} - \frac{l_1^2 c_{33}}{4}.$$

The input stiffness of the rotation platform can be calculated as

$$k_{in} = \frac{F_{in}}{d_{in}} = \frac{F_{in}}{2\Delta x} = \frac{L^2 - 4a_4 k_{rh}}{2(a_1 L^2 - 4a_1 a_4 k_{rh} + 4a_2 a_3 k_{rh})} \quad (17)$$

IV. EVALUATION OF 2-DOF ROTATION PLATFORM

In order to evaluate the analytical model and determine the characteristics of the 2-DOF decoupled rotational platform, finite element analysis (FEA) is carried out with the aid of ANSYS software. The finite element model (FEM) is established which is shown in Fig 5. The architectural parameters and physical parameters of the rotation platform are tabulated in Table I.

Fig. 5 FEM of the 2-DOF rotation platform.

TABLE I. THE ARCHITECTURAL PARAMETERS AND PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF THE ROTATION PLATFORM

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
r_h	1 mm	l_1	3.5 mm
t_h	0.4 mm	l_2	0.6 mm
h	6 mm	L	25 mm
r_b	1 mm	E	70 GPa
t_b	0.3 mm	ν	0.33
h_b	6 mm	ρ	2850 kg/m ³

During simulation analysis, zero displacements are assigned on the surfaces of the base to immobilize the mechanism. The input displacement in X-axis, $d_{in}=10\mu\text{m}$, is applied on the input terminal of the bridge-type mechanism.

The deformation behavior of the rotation platform is shown in Fig. 6. Figure 6 also illustrates the deformation behavior under the input displacements in X- and Y- axes. From the result it can be found that the rotations in X- and Y- axes are decoupled. The rotational angle can be calculated as 2.76 mrad, which is a little smaller than the result of analytical model, 3.2 mrad. By apply different amplitudes input displacements, the input stiffness of the rotation platform can be obtained, which is shown in Fig. 7. The input stiffness calculated by FEA is a little smaller than that of the analytical model. The reason of above errors is mainly the “displacement loss” effect arising from the combination of lever arm bending and connection flexure stretching which causes the actual amplification ratio to be smaller than the ideal value.

Fig. 6 Static analysis results by FEA: (a) rotation in single axis and (b) rotation in double axes.

Fig. 7 Relationship between the input displacements and input forces.

V. DISCUSSION

Intuitively, the influence laws of parameters L , l_1 and l_2 on the rotational angle are obtained easily. From Eq. (16) it can be found that if the input displacement is constant, the rotational angle is proportional to the distance L . The law that parameters l_1 and l_2 affect the rotational angle is the same as that of bridge-type mechanism. In this section, we focus on the influence of the parameters of the flexure hinge, the circular hinge and Hook joint.

Figure 8 shows the influence of the circular hinge on the rotational angle and input stiffness. The results are obtained under the precondition that other parameters are constant as shown in Table I. From Fig. 8 (a) we can find that the rotational angle of the platform increases gradually with the increase of the radius of the circular hinge. Moreover the relationship between the rotational angle and the radius is approximately linear. It can be also obtained that when the radius is constant, the smaller the minimal thickness of the hinge, the greater the rotational angle. From the relationship between the input stiffness and the radius of the circular hinge shown in Fig. 8 (b), it can be found that the input stiffness of the platform reduces as the increase of the radius of the circular hinge. The input stiffness decreases faster when the radius is small, i.e., $r_b < 1\text{mm}$, and the input stiffness decreases slower when the radius is large, i.e., $r_b > 1.5\text{mm}$. It can be also found that the input stiffness is not proportional to the radius of the circular hinge. When the radius is constant, input stiffness reduces with the increase of the minimal thickness of the hinge. Specifically, when the minimal thickness t_b is very small, i.e., $t_b = 0.1\text{mm}$, the radius has no effect on input stiffness, basically.

Figure 9 shows the influences of the Hook joint on the rotational angle and input stiffness of the rotation platform. From Fig. 9 (a) we can find that the rotational angle of the platform increases gradually with the increase of the radius of the Hook joint, but the relationship is nonlinear. When the minimal thickness is very small, i.e., $t_h = 0.1\text{mm}$, the radius has little influence upon the rotational angle. It can be also obtained that the smaller the minimal thickness of the Hook joint, the greater the rotational angle. On the contrary, the rotational angle of the platform reduces with the increase of the radius of the Hook joint. Specifically, when the minimal thickness t_h is very small, i.e., $t_h = 0.1\text{mm}$, the radius of Hook joint has no effect on input stiffness.

Fig. 8 Influences of the circular hinge on the rotation platform: (a) on the rotational angle and (b) on the input stiffness.

Fig. 9 Influences of the Hook joint on the rotation platform: (a) on the rotational angle and (b) on the input stiffness.

Compared with Figs (8) and (9), it can be found that the influences of the Hook joint on the rotational angle and the input stiffness in much smaller than those of the circular hinge. Therefore during the design stage of the rotation platform the circular hinge, that is the bridge-type mechanism, should be paid more attentions to obtain an ideal rotational angle and input stiffness. Moreover if the thickness of the flexure hinge is too small, the choice of the radius will be limited.

In order to guarantee the platform rotation angles in the X- and Y- axes are the same, we set the thickness of the Hook joint to be equal with that of the bridge-type mechanism, i.e., $h=h_b$. The influences of the thickness of flexure hinge h on rotational angle and input stiffness are obtained. From Fig. 10 it can be seen that the thickness of flexure hinge h has no effect on the rotational angle and the input stiffness increases linearly with increasing thickness. Therefore we can determine the thickness of the hinge by just considering the input stiffness of the rotation platform.

Fig. 10 Influence of the thickness of flexure hinge on the rotation platform.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this paper, we designed a novel 2-DOF decoupled rotation platform. The platform is driven by two PZT actuators and consists of base, bridge-type mechanism, Hook joint, pillar and upper platform. In the 2-DOF rotation platform the bridge-type mechanism is utilized to obtain large range rotational angle and the Hook joint is used to realize the rotation decoupling in X- and Y- axes. An analytical model for rotational angle and input stiffness calculation is established, which is evaluated by FEA. The influences of key parameters on the rotational angle as well input stiffness of the rotation platform are analyzed. We can obtain that the influence of the Hook joint on the rotational angle and the input stiffness is much smaller than that of the circular hinge in bridge-type mechanism and the circular hinge in the bridge-type mechanism should be paid more attentions to obtain an ideal rotational angle and input stiffness. Moreover thickness of flexure hinge h has no effect on the rotational angle and has a linear relationship with the input stiffness.

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